

Strength Tests of CFRP Joint Assembly Models for Tailplane Structure

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ABSTRACT

To obtain design and technical data, static and fatigue strength tests of four types of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) sub-structure models were conducted. These models are fundamental joint assemblies for an all-composite horizontal tailplane which is being planned in conjunction with advanced type of NAL-STOL research aircraft. The types of models include CFRP spar with rib, CFRP spar with metallic fitting, CFRP skin with stringer and CFRP stringer-stiffened panel. The experimental results indicate that static strength of the all types of models cleared the design ultimate. Numerical results of the stiffened panel agree fairly well with those of tested ones. For fatigue strength, reasonable values were obtained.

INTRODUCTION

Since composite materials have the advantage of low weight, high specific strength and stiffness as compared with those of conventional metallic materials, adaptation of composite to the primary structures will provide a considerable reduction in total structural weight for an aircraft. Although several kinds of composite are available, CFRP would be one of the promising materials which can be used for primary structures of a civil aircraft (1), (2).

The National Aerospace Laboratory of Japan has been promoting the program on the research and development of Quiet STOL aircraft since 1975. The program is classified in two parts, namely the development of STOL research aircraft and technical researches on advanced technology related to the aircraft. "Research on Structures", one of the technical researches, is currently being performed to obtain basic knowledge and technical data in applying CFRP to primary structures for a horizontal tailplane.

In the fiscal years of 1978 and 79, as the first step of the research, the static and fatigue tests were performed on the models of CFRP spar and rib element with corrugated web, and basic information as well as experimental data in use of CFRP as primary structural elements were obtained (3), (4). Succeedingly, joint assembly models of CFRP spar with rib, CFRP spar with metallic fittings, CFRP skin with stringer and CFRP stringer-stiffened panel were tested in 1980 and 81 as the second part of the program.

The work reported here is focused upon experimental study on the strength of four types of models above mentioned. The purpose of the tests were to evaluate ultimate strength and fatigue strength of jointed parts as well as to investigate failure mode of the models. For static test two pieces for each type were tested, while for fatigue test except stiffened panel four pieces were used.

DESCRIPTION OF MODELS

Laminate Construction

CFRP parts of models were composed of layers of eight-harness-satin (fabric) and uni-directional laminate (ud laminate). The normal thickness of fabric and ud laminate for one layer were 0.4 mm and 0.14 mm in cured state, respectively. The prepreg of fabric and ud laminate as well as the process of manufacturing adapted to the models were much the same as that used to the spar and rib elements tested as the first part of the program in 1978-79. More details about the materials and process should be referred to the previous report (3).

Fig. 1 illustrates laminate construction for spar, rib and stringer elements which were constructed with fabric and ud laminate, whereas Fig. 2 explains those for skin and panel elements containing ud laminate alone. In the figures, a fine line and a bold line indicate ud laminate and fabric, respectively. Direction 0° was determined to coincide with longitudinal direction of each element of a jointed model.

Fig. 1. Laminate Construction of Spar, Rib and Stringer

Skin element used for	Laminate construction	Dimension (mm)		
		A	B	C
S/F model	$+45^\circ/0^\circ_3/\mp 45^\circ$	60	120	1.0
S/S model		200	350	
S/P model	$(+45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ)_{sym}$	535	700	1.4

Fig. 2. Laminate Construction and Dimension of Skin

Geometry of Models

CFRP Spar with Rib (S/R model). Fig. 3 shows brief geometry of a S/R model where the depth of corrugated web was 17 mm for both spar and rib elements. They were assembled using aluminum alloy angles (7075-T6) and alloy steel bolts (NAS 1203). The jointed part of rib web was kept plane and thinner in its thickness than that of corrugated web as indicated in Fig. 1. Channel shape of aluminum alloy stiffeners (7075-T3C) were adhesively bonded to the end part of flat web and flanges, so that no failure occurs first at these support areas in loading.

CFRP Spar with Metallic Fittings (S/F model). Fig. 4 illustrates a S/F model, of which a spar element was the same as that used in S/R model explained above. Two metallic attachment fittings fabricated by welding of steel flanges (4130) and a steel web (ss41) were mounted to the both sides of the central part of a spar element using aluminum angles and steel bolts similar to a S/R model. Although metallic fitting should be mounted to one side in an actual structure, symmetry configuration was selected in this case for convenience of loading apparatus. On the central part of top flange cap, a skin element was fixed by eight countersunk bolts (NAS 1203). Four of them, positioned at central part, connected through the skin, spar flange and metallic flange, while the rest four jointed skin and spar flange.

CFRP Skin with Stringer (S/S model). Since a S/S model was planned to test under tensile loading, it took the form of long and slender as shown in Fig. 5. End of a skin and a stringer element were fixed with eight countersunk bolts. Other end of the stringer was also bolted to a dummy fixture of steel plate, whereas the opposite end of the skin was double lapped with thin steel plate. Because of such geometry, in direction of thickness there existed a slight offset between loading axes of skin side and stringer side.

CFRP Stringer-Stiffened Panel (S/P model). The laminate constructions of a panel and a stringer elements for a S/P model were the same as that adapted for a S/S model. A S/P model, however, was to be subjected to compressive loading, and consequently there were big differences in their forms as well as in assembly method between S/S and S/P models.

A S/P model, shown in Fig. 6, was composed of a panel element and three stringers which adhesively bonded and moreover fastened by steel bolts with hexagonal head to a surface of the panel. Since the use of this type of bolt allowed no countersunk holes at the panel, possibility of local failure around bolt hole could be decreased. Top and bottom parts of the stiffened panel were molded with wood-metal so as to avoid local failure or buckling at the edges. The edges of the molded ends had been carefully machined flat and to be kept parallel in order to satisfy uniform loading condition.

Fig. 3. CFRP Spar/Rib Model

Fig. 4. CFRP Spar/Fitting Model

Fig. 5. CFRP Skin/Stringer Model

Fig. 6. CFRP Stiffened Panel

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Test Program

Static tests were performed on two models for each of S/R, S/F, S/S and S/P models, for the purpose of assessing behaviours of various jointed parts, ultimate strength and failure mode of the models. These models represent key joints in assemblage of structural parts. Fatigue tests were conducted on four models for each type of three except S/P type, in order to investigate behaviours under cyclic loading, fatigue life and residual strength. As a load ratio, $R=0.1$ was selected throughout the fatigue tests.

For both static and fatigue tests of all the models except S/P models, the same loading and measuring systems were used so as to avoid influences exerted by the difference of testing facilities. For compressive test of S/p models, a universal testing machine was applied. Direction and location of applied load as well as positions and conditions of support points of the models were sketched briefly in Fig. 7.

Loading Procedure

As the loading apparatus, a set of electro-hydraulic servo controller system which includes a hydraulic jack, a pump unit, a load cell, servo valves, feedback circuit, controller and etc., was prepared. For S/R models, load was applied to the prescribed location on top flange, where a hemispherical bearing attached, through extension rod connected to the jack. Load magnitudes were measured by a 10 tonf MTS load cell placed in series with the rod and the jack. To retain simply supported conditions, hemispherical bearings and a roller were set under the bottom flanges of the spar and the rib elements, respectively.

For S/F models supported with two rollers, a U shape jig whose ends were pin connected to metallic fittings was employed to ensure symmetric loading. Load was transmitted through extension rod to the center of the U shape jig which located beneath the center of the model.

S/S models were loaded through the pin connection at the end of skin side, while opposite end hunged with a rod attached to a heavy steel frame, to prevent lateral deflection caused by its own weight. At the end of hanging rod a universal joint was attached so that the model under loading could be free from bending constraint.

Loading for a S/P model was done as standard manner of compression test, since an ordinal testing machine applied to the test. Namely the model whose molded edges kept up and down was set between heavy and thick loading discs attached to cross head and to rigid frame of the machine, while side edges of the panel were supported with knife-edged device.

Typical test arrangements are pictured in Fig. 8 which shows S/F model positioned on the roller supports attached to steel frames. Fig. 9 illustrates set up view of S/P model placed between loading discs of the testing machine.

Fig. 7. Loading and Support Conditions for Tests

Fig. 8 Test Arrangement (S/F model)

Fig. 9 Compression Test (S/P model)

Measurement System for Strain, Displacement and AE

A set of digital strain amplifier with manual scanners and a printer was used to measure strains more than 100 points in static tests. Displacements were measured directly from digital dial gauges and by transducers. In fatigue tests three points of strains, displacement of center and magnitude of cyclic load were measured for all the time by using dynamic strain amplifier. An AE sensor was installed to CFRP part of models in every tests and rate count and total count of AE signals were recorded.

RESULTS

Static Tests

The results obtained are shown in Table 1 and 2. In Table 1 strains are at rib web of S/R model and at center on skin element of S/F model, whereas for S/S model measured at the edges of countersunk holes. Analytical results by finite element method on panel buckling load agree fairly well with tested ones as shown in Table 2. In calculation of Euler buckling, end constraint factor $C=4$ was adapted. In a practical case, however, $C=3.75$ was proposed for stiffened panel of aluminum alloy (5), whereas $C=3.71$ would give good agreement with experiment in this study (6).

S/R model. Strains at both sides of the failure point are shown in Fig. 10, which suggest that at the critical area of the web local shear buckling occurred and out-of-plane displacement increased to failure. The location and failure

Table 1. Results of Static Tests

Model No.	Ult. P (kN)	Strain (%)	Design P (kN)
S/R 1	28.4	1.48	15.5
2	25.5	1.41	
S/F 1	37.4	0.61	22.1
2	37.0	0.44	
S/S 1	35.3	0.74	34.5
2	33.3	0.70	

Table 2. Results of Compression Tests

Model No.	Panel Buckling (kN)		Max. Load(kN)	
	Experiment	Cal.	Exp.	Cal.*
S/P 1	80.4	77.7	173.0	186.2
2	83.3	79.4	172.7	

*Euler Buckling Load for $C=4$

mode shown in Fig. 11 were almost same for models No. 1 and for No. 2.

Fig. 10. Load- Strain of S/R-1,2

Fig. 11. Failure at Rib Web

S/F model. The fastener holes on the skin element were crushed as shown in Fig. 12, while other components, spar element and fittings were little damaged. AE counts are shown in Fig. 13 which indicates that AE started even in lower loading levels and total count remarkably increased near final state.

Fig. 12. Failure at Skin(S/F-2)

Fig. 13. Result of AE Counts(S/F-1)

S/S model. After failure, skin and stringer elements were completely separated because of bending effect attributed to the offset. Fig. 14 shows the damaged area of skin element, while no apparent damage was observed in stringer element as well as metallic fasteners.

S/P model. Panel buckling with nine half waves in direction of loading, a half wave between stringers in lateral direction occurred first. The mode shape was determined by the strain distributions measured during the test. Increase of load after panel buckling yielded whole buckling in the model similar to Euler buckling mode, and final failure took place at the edges of stringer webs with a crash sound. Fig. 15 illustrates the final state at loading edges where delamination can be observed. On the adhesively bonded surface of stringer flanges, no peeling was recognized, and little damage around the fastener holes of the panel were also observed.

Fig. 14. Damage Around Bolt Holes

Fig. 15. Final Failure at Stringer Web

Fatigue Tests

The results of all fatigue tests including retest and residual test in static are tabulated in Table 3. In Figs. 16-18, numerals near circles correspond to model numbers.

S/R model. With models No. 3 and 4, no failure occurred until 10^6 cycles under the load initially set, therefore retests were conducted with increased loads. The critical part was rib web near jointed angle as same as in the static tests. Loading frequency was from 0.5 to 2.5 Hz depending on magnitude of load and displacement at loading point.

Table 3. Fatigue Life

Model No.	Max. Load (kN)	Life N
S/R 3	16	$>10^6$
3*	23	1282
4	22	$>10^6$
4*	23	67870
5	25	36
6	24	139
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S/F 3	26	37890
4	28	31455
5	24	39680
6	18	$>2 \times 10^6$
6**	25.9	
<hr/>		
S/S 3	25	100535
4	28	8016
5	23	$>10^6$
5***	34	
6	24	74673

* retest with increased load
 ** residual strength
 *** residual with constraint

Fig. 16. Load-N Relation on S/R Model

Fig. 17. Load-N Relation on S/F Model

Fig. 18. Load-N Relation on S/S Model

S/F model. For the model No. 6, the static test after 2×10^6 cyclic loading was performed to examine residual strength and failure mode. In all the tests, shear failure at the heads of countersunk bolts initiated, and failure around the bolt holes on the skin element followed. For model No. 5, bolt rupture in a jointed angle followed, while for No. 6 fatigue crack at the corner of an angle was observed.

S/S model. For all the models except No. 5, failure mode are the same as those in the static tests, namely the compressive side of fastener holes on the skin were crashed and no apparent damage was found in stringers. It should be noted that the residual strength test on model No. 5 was performed under the constraint to prevent out-of-plane deformation at the critical part of the skin and different failure mode from others was resulted. Consequently, it is suggested that the constraint probably allowed to give excess loading as compared in a test without constraint.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are obtained by the investigation.

S/R model. For all the models, both in the static and fatigue tests, shear failure occurred in the flat part of rib web next to joint angle. Critical area and failure mode were the same in both tests. The results suggest that the more strength could be expected by adapting the laminate construction used in corrugated web to the flat web.

S/F model. The critical part for static strength was edges of countersunk holes in the skin element, whereas in the fatigue tests rupture of metallic bolts initiated. Although they cleared the design ultimate load, more study to stiffen the part and to select proper fasteners should be studied.

S/S model. Failure took place around the fastener holes in the skin, while no visual damage was observed in the stringer element. To increase the joint strength, alternative method to fasten thin plate without countersunk should be introduced.

S/P model. Skin buckling occurred first at 46 percent of ultimate load and Euler buckling followed. Final failure took place at the edges of stringers where delamination of webs were observed. Numerical results coincided with those of the experiment, and validity of the method of analysis proposed was confirmed.

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